

The Factors Influencing Purchase Decisions and Consumer Satisfaction for Coffee Beverages through E-Commerce in Lombok Island

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Abstract: When making purchases online, consumers are faced with various considerations. After making a purchase, consumers do not stop at the consumption stage but will evaluate the product, which can result in satisfaction or dissatisfaction. The method used in this research is descriptive. The unit of analysis in this study is the urban community residing on Lombok Island who consume coffee beverages purchased through e-commerce. This research was conducted on Lombok Island, with 150 respondents determined through purposive sampling. The data sources in this study are primary data and secondary data. Data was collected using interview techniques with questionnaires that were then orally submitted and distributed to the respondents using WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram. This study aims to analyze the importance and performance levels of product quality, product safety, ease of obtaining, service, weather, location, Income, Lifestyle, and gender for urban consumers; (2) analyze the satisfaction level of urban consumers with coffee beverages through e-commerce; (3) analyze the influence of product quality, product safety, ease of obtaining, service, weather, location, Income, Lifestyle, and gender on urban consumers' purchase decisions for coffee beverages through e-commerce; (4) analyze the influence of product quality, product safety, ease of obtaining, service, weather, location, Income, Lifestyle, gender, and purchase decisions on urban consumer satisfaction.

Keywords: Purchase Decisions, Consumer Satisfaction, E-Commerce, CSI, IPA, SEM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture plays an influential role in driving the Indonesian economy. In 2022, the agricultural sector's contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) was significant, around 12.40%. The plantation subsector is the most significant contributor to the agricultural sector. In 2022, the contribution of the plantation sub-sector to the total GDP was 3.76%, and 30.32% to the agricultural sector. One of the plantation commodities that has a significant role in Indonesia's economic activities is coffee (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2022).

Coffee is an important export commodity for Indonesia as a foreign exchange earner. In 2022, Indonesia ranked third as the largest coffee producer in the world, with a production amounting to 794.8 thousand tons, an increase of 11% compared to the previous year (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2023). Along with the growth in coffee production, coffee consumption

continues to increase. In 2021, Indonesia's coffee consumption reached 5 million 60-kg bags, equivalent to 300,000 tons, with a growth of 8% (Katadata Insight Center, 2024). According to Maris (2019), coffee is now not only popular among the elderly but has also become a growing trend among all age groups. Coffee is no longer just a drink to dispel sleepiness or provide energy but has become a lifestyle.

As times evolve, consumers' lifestyles are shifting towards an all-online lifestyle due to the many benefits of online shopping, such as saving time, easier product access, and increased effectiveness and efficiency. In 2020, 93% of product or service searches were conducted online, and 87.1% of purchases were made online (databooks, 2021). According to data from the Katadata Insight Center (2024), throughout 2023, the most purchased products by consumers through e-commerce platforms Shopee, Tokopedia, and Blibli were food and beverages, with sales reaching IDR 118 trillion or about 20.4% of the total sales value in the Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) sector. The highest sales proportion was in the beverage category, with a percentage of 18.3%, and coffee was the most purchased product, accounting for 62% of the total beverages sold.

E-commerce plays a crucial role in increasing the sales of coffee beverages in Indonesia. It can expand market access, create jobs, and positively impact supporting business sectors, ultimately accelerating Indonesia's economic growth (Rahmawati & Erawati, 2021). E-commerce encompasses distribution, sales, purchases, marketing, and product service activities conducted via the Internet. With e-commerce, people's activities have become more effective and efficient (Nangi & Sukaatmaja, 2015).

The e-commerce trend has spread throughout Indonesia, including the province of West Nusa Tenggara. Bank Indonesia NTB recorded that e-commerce transaction values in NTB increased by 97.35% in 2021 compared to the previous year. Additionally, the launch of many online shopping sites in NTB indicates that the interest in online shopping among NTB residents is similar to that of larger islands. Coffee is a flagship product distributed through the NTB Mall e-commerce, which is highly favored by consumers (Satu Data NTB, 2020).

According to CBS (*Central Bureau of Statistics*) data (2023), the average per capita expenditure of NTB residents for beverages is relatively high, particularly for ready-to-drink coffee. West Nusa Tenggara is one of the provinces with high coffee consumption, especially among the residents of Lombok Island. Based on preliminary surveys conducted by the researchers, the people of Lombok Island, known as the Sasak tribe, have a long-standing tradition of coffee drinking. When purchasing coffee, the people of Lombok Island have specific considerations, as many sellers on e-commerce platforms offer the same products with varying prices and qualities. Consumers are aware of the risks associated with online purchases, so several factors can influence their decision to buy coffee beverages through e-commerce, such as product quality, ease of obtaining, service, product safety, Income, Lifestyle, environment, gender, etc.

After making a purchase, consumers do not stop at the consumption stage but will evaluate the product. If a product's performance meets consumer expectations, it will result in satisfaction. However, if a product's quality exceeds consumers' expectations, consumer satisfaction will be achieved. Satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises from comparing a product's perceived performance (result) to its expectations (Atma & Nio, 2019). To meet consumer satisfaction for coffee beverages, coffee business players must be able to meet consumer perceptions or desires by offering the best quality coffee beverages, such as improving product quality, ensuring product safety and halal status, making products easily accessible, and providing maximum service to make it easy for consumers to obtain the desired coffee beverages.

Research on coffee consumer behavior has been extensively studied before. Studies on factors influencing coffee purchase decisions have been conducted by Justice (2022), Safrida *et al.* (2020), and Pratama *et al.* (2022). Meanwhile, research on coffee consumer satisfaction has been conducted by Vista (2023), Jufriyanto (2020), Siti (2018), dan Refikasa (2021). The difference between this research and previous studies is that this study analyzes the factors influencing purchase decisions and consumer satisfaction with coffee beverages through internal and external factors for urban consumers, categorized into three classifications:

1. Product Attributes are directly related to the coffee beverage, such as product quality, safety, accessibility, and service.
2. Geographic Factors are influenced by geographic conditions such as weather and location.
3. The socioeconomic conditions of consumers, such as Income, Lifestyle, and gender, influence socioeconomic factors.

I. 1 Hypotheses:

Figure 1: Hypotheses Model

- X1: Product quality affects purchasing decisions.
- X2: Product quality affects consumer satisfaction.
- X3: Product safety affects purchasing decisions.
- X4: Product safety affects consumer satisfaction.
- X5: Service affects purchasing decisions.
- X6: Service affects consumer satisfaction.
- X7: Ease of access affects purchasing decisions.
- X8: Ease of access affects consumer satisfaction.
- X9: Weather affects purchasing decisions.
- X10: Weather affects consumer satisfaction.
- X11: Location affects purchasing decisions.
- X12: Location affects consumer satisfaction.
- X13: Income affects purchasing decisions.

- X14: Income affects consumer satisfaction.
- X15: Lifestyle affects purchasing decisions.
- X16: Lifestyle affects consumer satisfaction.
- X17: Gender affects purchasing decisions.
- X18: Gender affects consumer satisfaction.
- X19: Purchasing decisions affect consumer satisfaction.

II. METHODS

The method used in this research is descriptive. The unit of analysis in this study is the consumers or the community of Lombok Island who live in urban areas, consume coffee beverages and purchase through e-commerce. The number of respondents is 150, determined by purposive sampling. There are two sources of data in this study: primary data and secondary data. Data was collected using interview techniques with a questionnaire, which was then submitted orally and distributed to the respondents using social media platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Consumer Evaluation of Importance and Performance Levels

Table 1. Assessment of Performance Levels and Importance of Attributes for Urban Consumers

No	Parameter	Average Importance Level	Importance Rank	Average Performance Level	Performance Rank
1.	Product Attributes				
	a. Product Quality	4,23	2	3,58	4
	b. Product Safety	4,30	1	3,63	3
	c. Service	3,99	4	3,73	1
	d. Ease of Access	4,06	3	3,51	6
2.	Geographical Factors				
	a. Weather	3,17	8	3,49	7
	b. Location	3,53	6	3,53	5
3.	Socioeconomic Factors				
	a. Income	3,38	7	3,43	8
	b. Lifestyle	2,89	9	3,37	9
	c. Gender	3,55	5	3,67	2
Average		3,68		3,55	

Source: Primer Data Processed (2024)

Table I shows that the average importance level for urban respondents is 3.68, while the average performance level across all attributes is 3.55. This indicates that the indicators studied are significant considerations for urban consumers when purchasing coffee beverages through e-commerce. Overall, the average performance level for rural respondents is nearly equal to the average importance level, with a difference of only 0.13. This suggests that the performance provided by coffee beverage producers adequately meets the desires of urban consumers purchasing through e-commerce on Lombok Island. Upon closer inspection per indicator, there are several indicators where performance levels are lower than consumer expectations, indicating that companies should improve or enhance performance in these areas to meet consumer desires or expectations.

B. Importance Performance Analysis (IPA)

Table I shows that consumers' average importance level is 3.68, and the average performance level is 3.55. These values serve as the axes for the Cartesian diagram of the Importance Performance Analysis (IPA), resulting in four quadrants: Quadrant I (High Priority), Quadrant II (Maintain Performance), Quadrant III (Low Priority), and Quadrant IV (Excessive). The Cartesian diagram of the Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) factors influencing purchasing decisions and consumer satisfaction with coffee beverages from the perspective of urban consumers can be seen in Figure I.

Figure 1: The Cartesian diagram of the Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) factors influencing purchasing decisions and consumer satisfaction with coffee beverages from the perspective of urban consumers

Caption:

Quadrant I (High Priority)

Ease of Access (4)

Quadrant III (Low Priority)

Weather (5)

Location (6)

Income (7)

Lifestyle (8)

Quadrant II (Maintain)

Product Quality (1)

Product Safety (3)

Service (3)

Quadrant IV (Excessive)

Gender (9)

1. Quadrant I (High Priority)

Quadrant I indicates attributes considered necessary by consumers but which companies still need to fully meet according to consumer expectations, resulting in consumer dissatisfaction. Factors in this quadrant need attention, prioritization, and performance improvement. One attribute in Quadrant I is ease of access. For consumers, obtaining a product quickly and efficiently is preferable. E-commerce is expected to facilitate this, providing clear information on product availability, product variety, and diverse payment methods such as mobile banking, e-wallets, cash on delivery, and other payment options. According to interview results, one advantage of purchasing coffee beverages via e-commerce is that consumers avoid queues and crowds and may find it cheaper due to quick access to promotional features. Producers must improve product security performance to achieve consumer satisfaction and loyalty, leading to repeat purchases. Overall, online purchasing features already sufficiently facilitate consumer access to coffee products, though consumers often complain about producers' timeliness in delivering ordered coffee beverages to urban consumers.

2. Quadrant II (Maintain)

Factors in Quadrant II have high expectations and performance levels. Quadrant II includes factors considered crucial by consumers, where producers' performance meets consumer expectations. These factors support consumer satisfaction, so companies must maintain them as they enhance the product's appeal to consumers. Based on research, factors in Quadrant II include:

a. Product Quality

Urban consumers consider product quality crucial, and producers already meet or exceed consumer expectations regarding coffee beverage quality. Product quality includes taste resulting from ingredient combinations and product durability, condition upon arrival, and packaging quality. Producers must sustain product quality to retain consumer preference for coffee beverages and prevent switching to other types of beverages.

b. Service

Service is crucial for consumer comfort when purchasing a product. Producers' service performance already meets consumer expectations. In purchasing coffee via e-commerce, service includes prompt and effective responses from producers, guarantees in case of delivery errors, and handling consumer feedback. Producers must consistently meet consumer expectations to foster customer loyalty and positively impact the company's reputation.

c. Product Safety

Consumer safety regarding coffee products is crucial, and producers' performance already meets consumer expectations in rural and urban areas. Consumers prioritize product safety due to its impact on health. Unsafe coffee may contain harmful chemicals, contaminants, or additives. Producers must maintain product safety by ensuring coffee products are free from harmful substances and safe for consumption.

3. Quadrant III (Low Priority)

Quadrant III includes factors considered less important or influential to consumers, with relatively low company performance levels. These factors have minimal impact on perceived benefits by consumers, suggesting potential performance improvements or enhancements. Attributes in Quadrant III for urban consumers include:

a. weather

Due to their consumption habits, consumers consider weather less critical. Most respondents in this study consume coffee regardless of weather conditions. The availability of coffee varieties that suit consumer preferences based on weather types diminishes weather's importance. For instance, during hot weather, consumers may purchase cold coffee variants, while during cold weather, warm variants may be preferred.

b. location

Location is not a significant consideration for consumers as they can consume coffee beverages anywhere and anytime. E-commerce enables consumers to access coffee beverages from distant locations. Consumers with busy schedules can also enjoy coffee beverages. Location attributes are in Quadrant III, indicating both low company performance and low consumer importance or expectations, suggesting producers need not prioritize improvements in location attributes as consumers do not heavily consider this when purchasing and consuming coffee beverages.

c. Income

Income is not crucial for rural consumers when purchasing coffee via e-commerce, as coffee prices are affordable and commensurate with perceived benefits received. The quantity of coffee purchased via e-commerce is independent of Income, as consumers buy according to their needs.

4. Quadrant IV (Excessive)

Quadrant IV includes factors considered less important by consumers, yet companies have provided excellent or satisfactory performance, leading to perceived excessive performance. According to urban consumer perceptions, gender is a factor in Quadrant IV.

Gender is considered less critical by rural consumers when purchasing coffee via e-commerce, yet producers have high-performance levels in this aspect. This perception may stem from the questionnaire distribution, where most respondents, predominantly women, indicated the highest average in the indicator "buying and consuming coffee only when there is work/activity that requires more time and energy than usual." This implies that female consumers only purchase and consume coffee at specific times, such as during increased work or other activities, suggesting producers need not overly emphasize performance in gender-specific factors.

The calculation results represent the overall assessment of all attributes. Upon reviewing the importance and performance levels, it is evident that several attributes need to meet consumer criteria. Therefore, companies must improve the performance of these attributes to satisfy the 27.40% of urban consumers who still feel dissatisfied or have yet to experience maximum satisfaction with coffee beverages purchased through e-commerce. Among these factors, product safety stands out with a weighted score of 0.49 or a satisfaction index of 9.73%. Conversely, Lifestyle has the lowest satisfaction level, with a weighted score of 0.32, corresponding to a satisfaction index of 6.40%.

C. Analysis of Customer Satisfaction Levels

Table 2. Calculation of Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI) for Coffee Beverage Consumers in Rural and Urban Areas

No	Indikator	Mean Importance Score (MIS)	Mean Satisfaction Score (MSS)	Weight Factor (WF) (%)	Weight Score (WS)
1.	Product Attributes				
	a. Product Quality	4,23	3,63	12,80	0,46
	b. Product Safety	4,30	3,75	13,00	0,49
	c. Service	3,99	3,72	12,10	0,45
	d. Ease of Access	4,06	3,65	12,00	0,45
2.	Socioeconomic Factors				
	a. Weather	3,17	3,53	9,57	0,34
	b. Location	3,53	3,54	11,00	0,38
	Socioeconomic Factors				
	a. Income	3,38	3,59	10,00	0,37
	b. Lifestyle	2,89	3,67	8,72	0,32
	c. Gender	3,55	3,53	10,70	0,38
Total Perkotaan		33,1	32,6	100	3,63
CSI Perkotaan (%)		72,60			

Sumber: Data Primer Diolah (2024)

D. Analysis of Factors Influencing Purchase Decisions

The outer model is a measurement model used to evaluate validity and reliability. There are three types of tests in outer model evaluation: convergent validity test, discriminant validity test, and reliability test (Ghozali, 2014).

Abbreviations: KP = Kualitas Produk; KMP = Keamanan Produk; PL = Pelayanan; KM = Kemudahan Mendapatkan; C = Cuaca; L = Lokasi; P = Pendapatan; GH = Gaya Hidup; G = Gender.

1. Measurement Model Evaluation (Outer Model)

Indicators are considered valid if they have outer loadings > 0.700 . Indicators that were dropped due to having outer loadings < 0.700 are KMP1 with an outer loading of -0.179 , PL3 with an outer loading of 0.444 , GH1 with an outer loading of 0.615 , GH2 with an outer loading of 0.453 , G3 with an outer loading of 0.378 , G4 with an outer loading of 0.458 .

Indicator KMP1, concerning the safety of beverages purchased through e-commerce, was dropped because it needed to reflect product safety for rural and urban consumers. According to respondents in this study, more explicit information about the materials or compositions must be provided, leading consumers to need more confidence in the ingredients' safety.

The next indicator dropped is PL3, concerned with friendly and good service. PL3 was dropped because it needed to adequately reflect good service for rural and urban respondents. This is likely due to the inconsistent quality of service consumers receive, where although good service is sometimes received, it is often perceived as less satisfactory.

The lifestyle variable dropped indicators GH1 and GH2. GH1 concerns consumers buying coffee through e-commerce due to social influences, while GH2 concerns purchasing coffee due to current trends. Both indicators are needed to reflect lifestyle factors adequately. This may be because respondents tend to purchase products based on other factors, such as high ratings or reviews.

The last dropped variable is gender. The Gender variable dropped indicators G3 and G4. G3 relates to consumers purchasing coffee through e-commerce and only consuming coffee at specific times or out of curiosity. G4 pertains to consumers who buy and consume coffee only when work or activities require more time and energy than usual. Both indicators did not adequately reflect gender variables. Even though consumers may purchase coffee through e-commerce at specific times, these indicators were considered inadequate in reflecting gender variables.

Figure 2. Outer Model Before Dropping

Figure 3. Outer Model After Dropping

The product quality variable consists of 5 indicators. The KP5 indicator, representing consistent product quality, has the highest loading factor value of 0.814. This reflects that if producers consistently provide high-quality products, purchasing decisions and consumer satisfaction in urban areas will be enhanced. After dropping, the product safety variable consists of 4 indicators. The KMP5 indicator, which represents the security of coffee beverages purchased through e-commerce due to good packaging, has the highest loading factor value of 0.851. This indicates that better packaging increases the security of coffee beverages bought via e-commerce, fostering consumer trust and potentially leading to purchase satisfaction. The

service and convenience variables did not undergo dropping since all indicators had loading factor values above 0.700. The PL5 indicator, which represents producers accepting criticism and suggestions from consumers, has the highest loading factor value of 0.882. This suggests that consumers are pleased when producers provide a feedback service. Consumers are more likely to purchase coffee beverages through e-commerce from producers offering feedback services because they can address dissatisfaction through criticism and suggestions. The convenience variable includes the KM3 indicator, which represents diverse payment methods, with the highest loading factor values of 0.887 for urban and 0.870 for urban respondents. This reflects that diverse payment methods increase purchasing decisions and satisfaction for rural and urban consumers.

The weather and location variables also did not undergo dropping since all indicators had loading factor values above 0.700. For the weather variable, the C5 indicator, representing how weather influences the amount of coffee consumed, has an outer loading value of 0.783. This indicates that weather affects urban consumers' coffee consumption, impacting the amount ordered via e-commerce. The location variable's L4 indicator, representing consumers purchasing and consuming coffee influenced by their work environment, suggests that urban respondents tend to buy coffee due to their workplace environment.

The income variable consists of 4 indicators after dropping one indicator. The P5 indicator, representing Income affecting coffee purchasing decisions through e-commerce, has the highest loading factor value of 0.870. This shows that Income significantly influences purchasing decisions and satisfaction with coffee bought through e-commerce. The lifestyle and gender variables each consist of 3 indicators after dropping two indicators. The GH5 indicator, representing consumers purchasing coffee through e-commerce after seeing others, has the highest outer loading value of 0.832. This indicates that purchasing decisions occur after observing others buy and consume coffee. For the gender variable, the G1 indicator, representing purchasing and consuming coffee as part of life, has the highest outer loading value of 0.905.

The purchasing decision variable consists of 2 indicators. The highest outer loading value is shown by the KPM2 indicator, representing seeking as much information as possible before purchasing, with a value of 0.913. This indicates that purchasing decisions require extensive information before buying coffee beverages.

Next, the measurement model evaluation continued with validity assessment through Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values. AVE values for each construct should be above 0.500. If AVE is less than 0.500, it is considered inadequate, indicating more error variance than indicator variance (Vinzi et al., 2010). Table 3 presents the output results of AVE values before and after dropping indicators for rural and urban areas.

Table 3. AVE Validity Test Output

Variabel Laten	Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Before dropping	Average Variance Extracted (AVE) after dropping
Product Quality	0,615	0,615
Product Safety	0,539	0,667
Service	0,628	0,628
Ease of Access	0,676	0,676
Weather	0,537	0,537
Location	0,578	0,578
Income	0,497	0,667
Lifestyle	0,498	0,674
Gender	0,482	0,729
Purchasing Decision	0,830	0,830
Consumer Satisfaction	0,804	0,804

Source: Processed Primary Data (2024)

After dropping indicators within each construct, the AVE values were above 0.500, indicating a well-fitting model where the Variance captured by the constructs is greater than the Variance resulting from measurement errors. With all variables validated, the next step involved measuring reliability values.

In the SEM-PLS method, reliability is assessed by Cronbach's alpha values, with 0.600 as the minimum acceptable threshold, and composite reliability should exceed 0.700. Table 4 shows the output results for reliability testing of constructs.

Table 4. Construct Reliability Test Output

Variabel Laten	Cronbach,s Alpha	Composite Reliability (rho_a)	Composite Reliability (rho_c)
Product Quality	0,844	0,849	0,889
Product Safety	0,835	0,849	0,889
Service	0,850	0,861	0,893
Ease of Access	0,881	0,890	0,913
Weather	0,784	0,787	0,853
Location	0,824	0,841	0,872
Income	0,833	0,834	0,889
Lifestyle	0,760	0,766	0,861
Gender	0,814	0,836	0,890
Purchasing Decision	0,795	0,795	0,907
Consumer Satisfaction	0,878	0,891	0,925

Source: Processed Primary Data (2024)

Based on Table 4 above, all variables in this study are reliable as they have Cronbach's alpha values above 0.600. Composite reliability values are above 0.700, indicating high internal consistency and reliability of each indicator in measuring constructs, demonstrating good internal consistency.

The next step involves testing discriminant validity by examining cross-loading values. Cross-loading values can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5.

	KP	KMP	PL	KM	C	L	P	GH	G	KPM	KK
KP1	0.793	0.537	0.522	0.583	0.713	0.351	0.298	0.269	0.325	0.458	0.465
KP2	0.759	0.579	0.549	0.490	0.692	0.133	0.248	0.319	0.378	0.349	0.367
KP3	0.787	0.495	0.451	0.473	0.693	0.158	0.231	0.285	0.200	0.380	0.403
KP4	0.768	0.608	0.461	0.491	0.682	0.297	0.219	0.284	0.277	0.384	0.450
KP5	0.814	0.610	0.502	0.552	0.723	0.307	0.238	0.348	0.372	0.452	0.468
KMP2	0.587	0.816	0.404	0.443	0.483	0.203	0.184	0.267	0.272	0.375	0.383
KMP3	0.655	0.775	0.405	0.478	0.589	0.203	0.218	0.313	0.215	0.235	0.283
KMP4	0.545	0.823	0.393	0.468	0.502	0.264	0.175	0.279	0.275	0.374	0.359
KMP5	0.598	0.851	0.512	0.490	0.557	0.149	0.152	0.361	0.255	0.386	0.435
PL1	0.460	0.420	0.722	0.492	0.429	0.175	0.167	0.262	0.148	0.450	0.482
PL2	0.531	0.442	0.863	0.607	0.465	0.192	0.239	0.383	0.296	0.516	0.550
PL3	0.371	0.354	0.742	0.428	0.365	0.019	0.075	0.302	0.138	0.432	0.434
PL4	0.549	0.447	0.739	0.577	0.456	0.170	0.215	0.280	0.126	0.401	0.428
PL5	0.586	0.432	0.882	0.606	0.511	0.163	0.235	0.286	0.297	0.524	0.553
KM1	0.555	0.487	0.616	0.840	0.534	0.267	0.260	0.358	0.284	0.597	0.610
KM2	0.550	0.370	0.535	0.780	0.469	0.253	0.267	0.233	0.283	0.388	0.429
KM3	0.554	0.484	0.565	0.870	0.538	0.261	0.320	0.328	0.310	0.527	0.567
KM4	0.542	0.530	0.576	0.833	0.525	0.244	0.381	0.449	0.241	0.449	0.527
KM5	0.534	0.469	0.525	0.787	0.482	0.195	0.273	0.244	0.241	0.484	0.515
C1	0.597	0.396	0.406	0.460	0.702	0.291	0.272	0.232	0.250	0.364	0.394
C2	0.645	0.488	0.475	0.472	0.707	0.210	0.175	0.294	0.283	0.341	0.369
C3	0.649	0.387	0.347	0.415	0.743	0.199	0.265	0.264	0.155	0.340	0.336
C4	0.696	0.567	0.406	0.429	0.726	0.282	0.209	0.251	0.268	0.354	0.368
C5	0.684	0.518	0.426	0.493	0.783	0.286	0.283	0.320	0.365	0.389	0.440
L1	0.268	0.274	0.169	0.258	0.281	0.780	0.380	0.276	0.426	0.313	0.294
L2	0.222	0.203	0.187	0.291	0.267	0.728	0.300	0.231	0.220	0.368	0.393
L3	0.219	0.094	0.075	0.136	0.232	0.735	0.358	0.288	0.217	0.192	0.244
L4	0.301	0.186	0.152	0.232	0.294	0.784	0.353	0.284	0.285	0.236	0.252
L5	0.229	0.130	0.061	0.135	0.229	0.772	0.339	0.270	0.268	0.205	0.184
P1	0.354	0.244	0.248	0.307	0.319	0.394	0.759	0.345	0.594	0.288	0.351
P2	0.251	0.198	0.217	0.197	0.270	0.258	0.781	0.403	0.391	0.256	0.268
P4	0.219	0.114	0.149	0.305	0.224	0.465	0.852	0.422	0.481	0.289	0.346
P5	0.212	0.162	0.174	0.355	0.267	0.348	0.870	0.439	0.425	0.339	0.379
GH3	0.334	0.316	0.284	0.354	0.320	0.318	0.437	0.814	0.285	0.384	0.440
GH4	0.316	0.301	0.354	0.354	0.312	0.287	0.353	0.816	0.410	0.486	0.474
GH5	0.290	0.301	0.296	0.254	0.281	0.255	0.434	0.832	0.356	0.348	0.393
G1	0.364	0.293	0.286	0.320	0.338	0.271	0.531	0.412	0.905	0.434	0.464
G2	0.344	0.294	0.180	0.282	0.330	0.372	0.435	0.457	0.863	0.364	0.388
G5	0.303	0.209	0.194	0.237	0.264	0.336	0.525	0.215	0.790	0.323	0.345
KPM1	0.462	0.322	0.539	0.547	0.434	0.334	0.276	0.410	0.382	0.909	0.819
KPM2	0.486	0.459	0.536	0.553	0.457	0.337	0.382	0.504	0.423	0.913	0.830
KK1	0.502	0.406	0.624	0.601	0.455	0.282	0.326	0.474	0.390	0.861	0.910
KK2	0.520	0.421	0.577	0.603	0.477	0.381	0.410	0.445	0.459	0.883	0.921
KK3	0.461	0.397	0.456	0.544	0.481	0.376	0.387	0.536	0.423	0.669	0.859

Source: Processed Primary Data (2024)

Based on Table 5, the analysis results show that the correlation values of latent variables with their indicators are higher than the correlation of latent variables with other indicators. This indicates that the latent constructs or variables predict their indicators better than others. According to Sarstedt et al. (2017), an indicator is said to pass the discriminant validity test if the cross-loading values with its variable are higher.

2). Evaluation of Structural Model (Inner Model)

After testing the measurement model or outer model to assess the validity and reliability of constructs, the next step involves evaluating the structural model by examining the R-squared and t-statistic values for path coefficient estimates obtained through bootstrapping. According to Chin (1998), R-squared values are interpreted as follows: > 0.67 is strong, 0.33-0.67 is moderate, 0.19-0.33 is weak, and < 0.19 is very weak. The R-squared values for this study can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. R-Square Values

Variable	R-Square	Interpretation
Purchasing Decision	0,497	Moderate
Consumer Satisfaction	0,837	Strong

Source: Primary data Processed (2024)

The R-squared value for urban consumers in the final model of this study is 0.497 for purchase decisions, categorizing it as moderate, while consumer satisfaction is 0.837, categorized as vital. This means that 49.7% of the variation in purchase decisions is explained by constructs like product quality, accessibility, service, product safety, weather, location, Income, Lifestyle, and gender, with the remaining 50.3% explained by other constructs not examined in this study. Consumer satisfaction, explained by variations in constructs like product quality, accessibility, service, product safety, weather, location, Income, Lifestyle, gender, and purchase decisions, amounts to 83.7%, with the remaining 16.3% explained by other constructs not examined in this study.

C. Hypothesis Testing

At this stage, the researcher will determine whether the hypothesis model is accepted or rejected. After a bootstrapping analysis, the original sample values (O), t-statistics, and p-values for path coefficient estimates are generated. The analysis results for rural respondents are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Path Coefficient Score

Relationship	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Hypothesis
Service -> Purchasing Decision	0.281	0.078	3.575	0.000	Accepted
Convenience -> Purchasing Decision	0.258	0.101	2.554	0.011	Accepted
Lifestyle -> Purchasing Decision	0.203	0.066	3.058	0.002	Accepted
Gender -> Purchasing Decision	0.187	0.081	2.312	0.021	Accepted
Purchasing Decision -> Consumer Satisfaction	0.731	0.058	12.601	0.000	Accepted

Source: Processed Primary Data (2024)

1. Influence of Service on Purchasing Decision (X5)

The influence of service on the purchasing decision of coffee beverages through e-commerce among urban consumers is 0.282, with a t-statistic value >1.96. Hence, the X5 hypothesis is accepted. The original sample value indicates a positive relationship between service and purchasing decisions. This is likely because, in urban areas, numerous producers and consumers sometimes need more satisfactory service during purchases. Hence, service becomes a consideration for urban consumers when purchasing coffee beverages through e-commerce. This research aligns with Sopiyan (2022), stating that service positively and significantly impacts purchasing satisfaction.

2. Influence of Convenience on Purchasing Decision (X7)

The influence of convenience on the purchasing decision of coffee beverages through e-commerce among urban consumers is 0.282, with a t-statistic value of 2.554. Hence, the X7 hypothesis is accepted for urban respondents. The original sample value is positive, indicating a positive relationship between convenience and purchasing decisions. Convenience is a significant factor in purchasing coffee beverages through e-commerce, as urban respondents often have busy schedules, making convenience a priority. This research is consistent with Rachmawati et al. (2019), stating that convenience significantly influences purchasing decisions.

3. Influence of Lifestyle on Purchasing Decision (X15)

The influence of Lifestyle on consumer satisfaction with coffee beverages through e-commerce among urban consumers is 0.203, with a t-statistic value of 3.058. The original sample value is positive, indicating a positive relationship between Lifestyle and consumer satisfaction, with a t-statistic value >1.96; hence, the X15 hypothesis is accepted for urban respondents. This is likely because consumers often agree with statements such as "consumers purchase coffee beverages through e-commerce after seeing friends/others" and similar indicators. This research aligns with Mu'ala (2023), stating that Lifestyle positively and significantly influences purchasing decisions.

4. Influence of Gender on Purchasing Decision (X17)

The influence of gender on the purchasing decision of coffee beverages through e-commerce among urban consumers is 0.188, with a t-statistic value of 2.312; hence the X17 hypothesis is accepted. This is likely because urban consumers, particularly women, tend to buy coffee beverages more frequently during tasks requiring more time and energy. Most respondents in this research are women who often work, leading them to purchase coffee beverages as work companions. Fitriani (2019) indicates that male and female consumers tend to make similar purchasing decisions when faced with the same context, concluding that women have more considerations in online purchasing decisions due to their feminine nature and sensitivity to online advertisements.

5. Influence of Purchasing Decisions on Consumer Satisfaction (X19)

The influence of purchasing decisions on consumer satisfaction with coffee beverages through e-commerce among urban consumers is 0.732, with a t-statistic value of 12.601; hence the X19 hypothesis is accepted. Purchasing decisions positively and significantly impact consumer satisfaction with coffee beverages bought through e-commerce. This indicates that better factors influencing purchasing decisions result in higher consumer satisfaction with coffee beverages bought through e-commerce in Lombok. Consumers who purchased coffee beverages through e-commerce in Lombok last year tend to seek extensive information before purchasing. Consumer satisfaction is shown by evaluating purchased products, making repeat purchases if satisfied, and recommending the product to others if satisfied. This research aligns with Karomah et al. (2022), stating that purchasing decisions positively and significantly influence shopping satisfaction in marketplaces.

Based on Table 7, it can be observed that the variables directly influencing purchase decisions are service quality, accessibility, Lifestyle, and gender. On the other hand, the variable directly influencing consumer satisfaction is purchase decision. These results contribute to the formulation of a new research model. The final model of this study is presented in Figure 5.

Information: —▶ = Significant;▶ insignificant

Figure 4. Final Research Model

The magnitude of effects between exogenous (independent) variables on endogenous (dependent) variables can be seen in the analysis results of direct and indirect effects in Table 8. In hypothesis testing, direct, indirect, and total effect values are used to observe the total predictive effect.

Table 8. Direct and Indirect Effects of Independent Variables on Consumer Satisfaction Through Mediating Variable (Purchase Decision)

Relationship	Direct (Original sample)	Influence (Yes/No)	Indirect (Original sample)	P Value Indirect	Influence (Yes/No)	Total Effects
Product Quality -> Purchasing Decision -> Consumer Satisfaction	-0,011	No	0,001	0,992	No	-0,009
Product Safety -> Purchasing Decision -> Consumer Satisfaction	-0,01	No	-0,027	0,663	No	-0,037
Service -> Purchasing Decision -> Consumer Satisfaction	0,074	No	0,206	0.000	Yes	0,281
Convenience -> Purchasing Decision -> Consumer Satisfaction	0,104	No	0,189	0,01	Yes	0,294
Weather -> Purchasing Decision -> Consumer Satisfaction	0,02	No	0,018	0,879	No	0,039
Location -> Purchasing Decision -> Consumer Satisfaction	0,016	No	0,094	0,15	No	0,11
Income -> Purchasing Decision -> Consumer Satisfaction	0,033	No	-0,05	0,425	No	-0,016
Lifestyle -> Purchasing Decision -> Consumer Satisfaction	0,057	No	0,149	0,004	Yes	0,205
Gender -> Purchasing Decision -> Consumer Satisfaction	0,188	No	0,138	0,021	Yes	0,182

Source: Processed Primary Data (2024)

Table 8 explains that no variables directly or indirectly affect consumer satisfaction through purchase decisions. Five variables directly influence purchase decisions: service quality, accessibility, Lifestyle, and gender. The variable directly influencing consumer satisfaction is purchase decision. The variable with the most significant direct influence on purchase decisions is service quality, with an original sample value of 0.282. This indicates that an increase in service quality of coffee beverages will increase the purchase decision of coffee beverages by 28.2%. The variable with the most significant direct influence on consumer satisfaction is purchase decision, with an original sample value of 0.732. This shows that urban consumers make purchase decisions by seeking as much information as possible about coffee products, which can increase consumer satisfaction with coffee beverages by 73.2%.

Variables that do not directly influence but indirectly influence consumer satisfaction through purchase decisions include service quality, accessibility, Lifestyle, and gender. Variables with direct and indirect influences with the most significant total effects are accessibility on consumer satisfaction, which amounts to 0.294. This indicates that an increase in accessibility of coffee beverages in Lombok Island through purchase decisions will increase consumer satisfaction with coffee beverages by 29.4%. Service quality has a total effect value of 0.218, indicating that improving the service quality of coffee beverages will increase consumer satisfaction by 21.8%. Lifestyle has a total effect value of 0.205, indicating that a higher lifestyle can increase purchase decisions and thus increase consumer satisfaction with coffee beverages by 20.5%. Gender has a total effect value of 0.182, indicating that a higher influence of gender in making purchase decisions can increase consumer satisfaction with coffee beverages by 18.2%.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and discussion results, several conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1. Consumers consider product safety, quality, accessibility, and service important when purchasing coffee beverages via e-commerce. The best factors are service, gender, product safety, and quality.

2. Based on the calculations, the Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI) for coffee beverages purchased via e-commerce by urban communities is 72.60%. This indicates that urban consumers are satisfied with coffee beverages purchased via e-commerce by rural and urban communities on Lombok Island.
3. From hypothesis testing results on urban respondents, it is known that service quality, accessibility, Lifestyle, and gender have a positive and significant influence on purchase decisions; product safety and Income have a negative and insignificant influence; and product quality, weather, and location have a positive and insignificant influence. The variable with the most vital and significant influence on urban respondents' purchase decisions is service quality, with an original sample value of 0.282.
4. From hypothesis testing results on urban respondents, it is known that purchase decisions have a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction; product quality and product safety have a negative and insignificant influence on consumer satisfaction; service quality, accessibility, weather, location, Income, Lifestyle, and gender have a positive and insignificant influence on consumer satisfaction. The variable with the most vital and significant influence on consumer satisfaction is purchase decision, with an original sample value of 0.732.

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